

EFFECTIVE WAYS OF GIVING STUDENTS AN UNDERSTANDING OF MUSIC CULTURE

Axmedova Inobat Baxodirovna

Urganch State University

Teacher of the "Music Education" department

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Abstract: In this article, opinions are given about effective pedagogical methods of raising students' understanding of musical culture and musical art.

Key words: Student and teacher, educational system, pedagogy, musical culture, K.D. Ushinsky.

Our great ancestors mentioned in their works that the role of music is important in the formation of perfect personality and human intelligence. The scientific and educational importance of the art of music culture education is highly appreciated among the specific "subsidiaries" of this field. That is why scholars who have gained worldwide recognition in the field of science, culture and art (Abu Nasr Farabi, Abdul Qadir Maroghi, Al Kindi, Abdurrahman Jami, Ibn Sina, Darvesh Ali Changi, Alisher Navoi) also in the field of science, they looked at it with special respect as both art and a means of education, and created large works and treatises on its various problems. These works, as the historical basis of musical-theoretical knowledge, have not lost their scientific and educational prestige even today. However, as in any field, there are modern requirements for the formation of a person in musical education, which is on the agenda as an order and need for education of every social era.

Singing in music classes not only has a positive effect on children, but also effectively affects the formation of their musical taste and musical outlook. Therefore, the complex of musical knowledge provided in the appropriate content and methodology will cultivate a stable interest in music in children, and the main thing is that they learn to distinguish between good music, genres, folk and classical music.

The results of the research conducted in the Lola preschool in Karshi showed that children began to sing, listen to music, and learn about the lives of composers with interest. Even the children who were indifferent to music lessons at first, eventually started coming to music lessons in high spirits, with the intention of learning something new. Children's interest and desire for various activities within the Music lesson increased. Many children have developed the skills to listen to music, sing songs, perform rhythmic movements in a literate, i.e., consciously approach.

Formation of skills in children to analyze the means of expression and form of a musical work has formed in them the skills to freely express their thoughts. The use of new pedagogical technologies in music training has increased children's interest in musical knowledge, including musical literacy. Children can easily solve musical puzzles, know notation, understand sound and its properties, and have a clear understanding of the means of musical expression.

Experiments have shown that the effectiveness of training depends on their proper organization. The "language" of music is understandable and close to everyone. Therefore, it is

an invaluable helper in shaping the young generation as a person, along with raising the spirit of people, giving joy and pleasure. Singing activities Music plays a leading role in children's education. This type of activity is close and understandable to children compared to other types of activity. Children love to sing. Singing is the leading activity of children's performance, and it occupies an important place in the musical and aesthetic education of children. A good song makes a child happy, develops and educates in all aspects. Unlike musical instruments, singing has a strong emotional impact. Because the song shows the artistic unity of text and music. Singing has a comprehensive effect on the development of a child's personality. The song serves to increase a person's intellectual maturity, expand his worldview, and enrich his imagination about the world around him.

In the process of singing, they perceive music more deeply, express their experiences and feelings more actively. The text of the song helps children understand the content of the music and learn the melody more easily. Children perceive better a melody performed by voice than a melody performed on an instrument. In the process of singing, children develop musical abilities: musical hearing ability, musical memory, sense of rhythm, and singing develops musical abilities: sense of meter and rhythm, musical hearing, sense of rhythm. The activity of singing in a group is necessary for the development of children's musical ability and performance skills. In the process of singing as a group in a group, the child tries to control his own voice performance, hear and observe the performance of his teachers and accompany them together, the feelings of collective unity, organization, and mutual friendship are cultivated.

It has been proven in practice that learning songs helps to form not only musical literacy, but also musical worldview, musical taste, musical thinking and similar qualities. From the first days when children come to preschool educational institutions, they have a high desire and interest in art, especially music. Therefore, special attention should be paid to the formation of children as individuals in music classes. It depends on the knowledge and creativity of the leader as a specialist, a master of his field.

Singing gives children a cheerful mood. It develops children not only mentally but also physically. Because when a child sings, his mouth, nose, respiratory tract, chest, and in general all his organs are active. During singing, the child should sit upright and freely. Education of singing skills in preschool children. In the process of singing, the respiratory tract also develops.

In the process of singing to children, attention is paid to the text and melody when the text and music are in harmony. In the song, the text and the musical melody are combined, having an emotional effect on the listener and evoking various feelings. This sensitivity is of great importance in child education. Even if the child does not understand the meaning of the song, even if he does not understand its content and music, he expresses an emotional reaction to the child from a young age. As the child develops, his speech and life skills help him to understand the song as a whole.

The process of singing unites children with a common mood, they learn to work together. They hear their comrades hurrying or lagging behind and call them to sing at the same pace. Singing is the main means of musical education. It is very close for children compared to other activities. By singing, they perceive music more actively. The text of the song helps to understand the melody of the song. In singing activities, children's musical abilities develop, as well as hearing memory and a sense of rhythm. Singing develops children's speech. When

singing as a group, the melody has a stronger effect on the child than the text. As K. D. Ushinsky noted: "In the song, especially in the choral group, there are emotions that educate the soul and bring it to jumbush»¹.

In many cases, we can observe a boy walking and singing a march, and a girl holding a doll. A child's voice is a natural instrument, because this instrument is present from a young age. That's why it accompanies him throughout his life and is used in various games. In addition, the song is used in other activities of the child's life. For example, when dancing, singing, playing children's instruments. Improvement of hearing ability develops from a young age of children. They hear the song, tune or melody when the music director or teacher sings it and sing it accordingly. Younger children can listen to songs between 2-3 notes. Children listen to adult tunes and then they try to sing the same tune as adults. In preschool children, the voice apparatus is not fully developed (vocal chords are not developed, thin, breath is weak, etc.). As the child develops, the body and singing organs also improve. A preschooler's voice will not be bright enough.

A child's natural voice is re 1 - si 1, that is, when the child sings higher and lower notes, the sound can be strained and compressed. This can cause damage to children's vocal cords. In order to avoid these problems, it is necessary to choose a well-thought-out and well-targeted repertoire. We focus on the range of singing.

Age Range

2 - 3 years old mi 1 - la 1

3-4 years re 1 — la 1

4-5 years re 1-si 1

5-6 years re 1 — si 1 (do 2)

6-7 years do 1 (re 1)-do 2

The given table contains the lower, upper and working range of children's voices. What should be considered when teaching children to sing and choosing a repertoire? Each song is selected with a view to the implementation of certain pedagogical goals. In it, each new song strengthens and develops the singing skills developed from the previous one. The diatonic of the song should be suitable for children's voice, artistic content, children's outlook and age.

It is recommended to choose songs according to the following requirements:

- ❖ *Appropriateness of the song's educational value, ideological content, musical structure and character to the age of the children.*
- ❖ *The simplicity of the song's text, its artistic quality, its compatibility with children's vocabulary, and the fact that it serves to develop their speech and thinking.*
- ❖ *The tone of the song, its character (cheerful, cheerful, march, melancholy, sad, festive, upbeat), key and tessitura, voice range should be suitable for the age of the children.*
- ❖ *Artistic features and expressiveness of the song, compatibility with children's perception, harmonic structure and melodiousness.*
- ❖ *The form of the song (1, 2-part or couplet) presence of refrain.*

When choosing a song, children are told a short, meaningful, figurative and interesting story. It inculcates the ideas of morality, nature, Motherland, and love in the minds of children and arouses interest in them. After the song is learned perfectly, their interest increases even

¹ Ushinskiy K.D. tom, publish. —M.: L., 1998.

more. Also, changing the forms of training (non-traditional training) prevents children from getting bored during training and keeps them interested.

Children are expected to learn 10-12 songs during the year. Tasks to achieve this: formation of pure intonation and singing skills in children; singing to children alone and with a tutor, performing in a cappella style; to develop the ability to hear music, the pitch of the melody, their length, the direction of the melody, the ability to hear oneself (when singing), the ability to hear one's mistakes during performance; voice development, achieving natural performance; to develop children's creative skills, to use their songs in choirs and games.

Singing skills In order for a child to sing properly, it is necessary to develop singing, vocal-choir skills. Singing skills. This is singing in the right position. In the process of singing, the child should sit leaning on the back of the chair instead of lifting the body. His hands are placed on his knees.

Vocal skills. This is voice production, breathing and diction. Breath should be short, light and noiseless. The words are pronounced clearly and burro.

Choir Qualifications. This is the interdependence of ensemble and structure. "Ensemble" is a French word that means "harmony" (slitnost), that is, a combination of strength and volume of voices. In this process, we need to achieve unison singing and timbre alignment.

Development of singing skills. Singing skills develop in the process of memorizing and teaching songs. Skill develops as the piece becomes more complex. In the process of education in kindergarten, he should know: Small and middle group - the music leader should be able to sing simple, uncomplicated songs with the help of a musical instrument. A large group - sings without an instrument only with the help of a music director or without a music director to the accompaniment of a musical instrument, must be able to distinguish the pitch and length of sounds, sit straight, upright, shoulders raised while singing.

Preschool preparatory group - can sing a memorized song expressively, remember to sing a previously memorized song, can hear the children next to him during the singing process, and the disadvantage - he can correct his mistakes, distinguish between up and down movement of sounds, must know the short length of the notes and the names of the notes.

Methods and ways of teaching to sing a song. Before teaching a song to children, the music director should introduce the song, tell about the composer, the text, the content of the work, in a word, the children should learn this song. is to arouse their interest in learning.

Song difficulties and ways to overcome them:

- ✓ *There are many jumping movements in the song. These are difficult for children to sing. Therefore, it is necessary to pay special attention to pure singing.*
- ✓ *Dotted rhythms are widely used in the song and they should be pronounced clearly.*
- ✓ *League notes. Such notes are mostly found at the end of sentences, and it is necessary to achieve correct and pure singing.*

The influence of the family environment on the formation and development of a child's personality is very large. The most important individual characteristics of a child are formed under the influence of the existing social and psychological environment in the family. The desire for the melody of the song is developed in the mind of the child through the mother. The relationship between parents and family members, and the relationship to art and musical culture play an important role in this. That is why it is not for nothing that family education is considered at the level of state policy in our Republic.

References:

1. Davletshin M. G. Psychology of a modern school teacher. - Tashkent, Uzbekistan, 1999.
2. Ishmuhammedov R, Abduqadirov A. Innovative technologies in education. - Tashkent, - Science, 2008.
3. Yoldoshev Sh, Usmanov S. Basics of pedagogical technology. - Tashkent, - Science, 2001 - year.
1. Ismailov Tohir. "Musical currents and the formation of Russian classical music". "Вестник магистратуры" 2021. №5 (116) ISSN 2223-4047;
2. Sharipova G. Music teaching methodology. TDPU, 2004.
3. Shakhlo Khakimovna Kharatova "Use of innovative technologies in the educational process" Vol. 3 No. 3 (2022): Science and Education;
4. Music teaching methodology and school repertoire. Educational and methodological complex of science. - SamSU, 2011.

